

COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING OF CAROTID ARTERY AND SIMULATION OF PLAQUE PROGRESSION

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Abstract

The main aim of this study was to simulate the plaque progression within the patient-specific carotid artery. In that order, the shear stress distribution was analyzed, since this mechanical parameter is associated with plaque progression. The 3D patient-specific model was created using computed tomography (CT) images and consisted of a finite element mesh. The 3D blood flow was governed by the Navier-Stokes equations and continuity equation. Mass transfer within the blood lumen and through the arterial wall was coupled with the blood flow and modelled by the convection–diffusion equations. Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL) transport in lumen of the vessel was described using Kedem-Katchalsky equations. The shear stress distribution, obtained after two time periods (baseline and follow-up), was compared, indicating that the zones of plaque progression and accumulation were associated with zones of lower shear stress. The simulation results have shown also that carotid lumen was reduced due to plaque progression.

Key words: Carotid artery, Plaque progression, Finite element analysis

1. Introduction

Atherosclerosis is a progressive disease characterized by inflammation, monocyte-macrophage migration, and lipid accumulation in the vessel wall. Atherosclerotic plaque progression is closely related to most severe cardiovascular syndromes, while mechanisms governing plaque progression and rupture have not been completely understood yet. Last years, there has been significant effort investigating these mechanisms with focus on computer, experimental and clinical analysis of plaque development in arteries [1]. Based on previous investigations [2], the main purpose of this paper was to computationally simulate plaque progression within patient-specific carotid artery, considering biomolecular parameters which affect plaque development. It is possible to predict the sites of plaque occurrence within the artery using computational simulation and knowing the biomolecular parameters (LDL, HDL, triglycerides) and adhesion molecules.

2. Materials and methods

The geometrical patient-specific model used for finite element analysis was created based on computed tomography (CT) data, using the segmentation software. Thereafter, several different software packages were employed in order to create 3D model based on finite element mesh. The final 3D model, suitable for computational simulation, consisted of eight-node brick elements. PAK solver was used for the simulation of blood flow and mass transport through the carotid artery, which was based on finite element method (FEM) [3]. The 3D blood flow was governed by continuity equation and Navier-Stokes equations. Convection–diffusion equations were used for modelling of mass transfer within the blood lumen and through the arterial wall, coupled with the blood flow. Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL) transport in carotid lumen was described using Kedem-Katchalsky equations. The boundary conditions were following: prescribed blood flow at the inlet of the carotid artery model and physiological resistance pressure at the arterial outlets. Two time periods were considered: baseline and follow-up.

3. Results and conclusions

Progression of atherosclerosis caused increasement of plaque volume and decrease of lumen diameter, which was confirmed after performed simulation. The zone of low shear stress and stagnant blood flow at the baseline, positioned at the internal carotid artery, indicated the greatest risk of plaque position. After the follow-up, carotid lumen was approximately 50% reduced comparing with baseline [1,2], which was followed by reduced blood flow through the stenotic zone, while at the same zone shear stress was increased. The maximum value of the shear stress for the obtained geometry was 7.00 Pa.

This type of simulation and determination of plaque location and progression in time for a specific patient shows a potential benefit for future prediction of this vascular disease using computer simulation. By using plaque progression simulation, plaque vulnerability assessment and clinical decisions can be based on multi-time CT scans and simulated “virtual” plaque progression.

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